

HIPPARCOS

On non-periodic Star Mapper grids and detection by means of matched filters

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1. INTRODUCTION

This note deals with three ideas related to the design and use of the HIPPARCOS Star Mapper:

- (1) that simple linear filters can be used for nearly-optimum real-time detection and measurement of stars crossing the Star Mapper grids;
- (2) that the use of non-periodic grids may have important advantages especially for the observation of faint stars without *a priori* positions, e.g. no slit ambiguity, and separate detection of transits across the vertical and inclined grids;
- (3) that the required linear filters can be implemented as 'folded filters' with little loss of accuracy but an order-of-magnitude reduction of computations.

Section 2 deals with the theoretical performance of the detection/estimation algorithm, while Section 3 gives a comparison with results of numerical simulations.

2. THEORY

2.1. Derivation of optimum linear estimator

Let n_i be the sequence of photoelectron counts produced by the Star Mapper. We shall discuss the possible detection of a stellar signal of known shape, but unknown amplitude and location, against a constant but unknown background count level. Thus, n_i is assumed to follow the Poisson distribution with mean

$$E(n_i) = b + a f(i - p), \quad (1)$$

where $f(x)$ is the known response function of the Star Mapper and b , a , and p are parameters to be estimated (background, amplitude, and position). Note that b and a are measured in counts per sampling interval (Δt) and p in multiples of $v\Delta t$, where v is the (constant) speed of scanning, $v = 150''/\text{sec}$.

Given the sequence of counts, the log-likelihood of a particular parameter vector $\underline{x} \equiv (b \ a \ p)$ is

$$\ell(\underline{x}) = - \sum_i (n_i - 1) + \sum_i n_i \ln[b + af(i-p)] - mb - a \sum_i f(i-p), \quad (2)$$

where $m = \sum_i 1$ is the number of samples considered. The maximum-likelihood estimate $\hat{\underline{x}}_{ML}$ is obtained by solving the likelihood equations $\partial \ell / \partial \underline{x} = \underline{0}$.

Unfortunately, the ML equations are non-linear and can only be solved by iteration. To avoid this complication we shall try the following scheme:

- (i) select a trial position p ;
- (ii) compute the best linear estimates $\hat{b}$, $\hat{a}$;
- (iii) compute a test statistic $L(\hat{b}, \hat{a})$ to decide whether a star is present at position p or not;
- (iv) proceed to the next position.

If steps (i) - (iii) are repeated for all integer values p , the detection/estimation algorithm can be represented as in Fig. 1.

The linear estimates must be of the form

$$\hat{b} = \sum_i \beta_i n_{i+p}, \quad \hat{a} = \sum_i \alpha_i n_{i+p}, \quad (3)$$

where the filter coefficients β_i, α_i are independent of the counting sequence. They should be chosen such that the resulting estimates are unbiased and (if possible) have minimum variance, when p is the true position. Since then $E(n_{i+p}) = b + af_i$, we find

$$\begin{aligned} E(\hat{b}) = b & \quad \leftarrow \quad \sum_i \beta_i = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i f_i \beta_i = 0, \\ E(\hat{a}) = a & \quad \leftarrow \quad \sum_i \alpha_i = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i f_i \alpha_i = 1. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Using $E(n_{i+p} n_{j+p}) = [b + af_i][b + af_j] + \delta_{ij}[b + af_i]$ we obtain the variances

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{\hat{b}}^2 &= b \sum_i \beta_i^2 + a \sum_i f_i \beta_i^2 \\ \sigma_{\hat{a}}^2 &= b \sum_i \alpha_i^2 + a \sum_i f_i \alpha_i^2. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

As for the ML estimates, we find that the minimum-variance estimates depend on the ratio $q = a/b$. Since optimum performance is most important for stars near the detection threshold, we should compute the filter coefficients for the corresponding value of q . Minimizing (5) under the constraints (4) we obtain

$$\alpha_i = \frac{M_0 f_i - M_1}{(M_0 M_2 - M_1^2)(1 + q f_i)}, \quad \beta_i = \frac{-M_1 f_i + M_2}{(M_0 M_2 - M_1^2)(1 + q f_i)}, \quad (6)$$

where $M_k = \sum_i f_i^k / (1 + q f_i)$.

We have no explicit formula for the variance of the position estimate $\hat{p}$. The Cramér-Rao lower bound suggests that $\hat{p}$ is essentially uncorrelated to $\hat{b}$ and $\hat{a}$, yielding the inequality

$$\sigma_{\hat{p}}^2 \geq b a^{-2} \left[\sum_i \frac{[f'(i)]^2}{1 + q f_i} \right]^{-1}. \quad (7)$$

2.2. Test statistic

To decide whether a star is present (hypothesis H_1) or not (H_0) we may test the log-likelihood ratio

$$L = \lambda(\hat{x}|H_1) - \lambda(\hat{x}|H_0). \quad (8)$$

From (2) we have

$$\lambda(\hat{x}|H_1) = -\sum_i (n_{i+p}!) + \sum_i n_{i+p} \ln(\hat{b} + \hat{a}f_i) - m\hat{b} - \hat{a} \sum_i f_i, \quad (9)$$

where the sums now extend over the range of the filters, and m is the number of filter points. Under the no-star hypothesis, $\hat{a} = 0$ and $\hat{b} = \sum_i n_{i+p}/m$. Then

$$\lambda(\hat{x}|H_0) = -\sum_i (n_{i+p}!) + \sum_i n_{i+p} \ln(\sum_i n_{i+p}/m) - \sum_i n_{i+p} \quad (10)$$

and

$$L = \sum_i n_{i+p} \ln[(\hat{b} + \hat{a}f_i)/\sum_i n_{i+p}] - m\hat{b} - \hat{a} \sum_i f_i + \sum_i n_{i+p}. \quad (11)$$

Taking the expectation of (11), putting $E(n_{i+p}) = \hat{b} + \hat{a}f_i$, we obtain the approximation

$$L(\hat{b}, \hat{a}) = \hat{b} G(\hat{a}/\hat{b}), \quad (12)$$

where the function

$$G(q) = \sum_i (1 + qf_i) \ln \frac{1 + qf_i}{1 + q \sum_j f_j/m} \quad (13)$$

may be tabulated in advance, or suitably approximated. For the presently described experiments we used the approximation

$$G(q) \approx Aq^2 / (1 + Bq), \quad A = [m \sum_i f_i^2 - (\sum_i f_i)^2] / (2m), \quad (14)$$

and adjusted the constant B to give the correct $G(q)$ at the detection threshold. If $\hat{a} < 0$, which is physically impossible, we set $L = 0$.

It is well known that $2L$ asymptotically follows the non-central chi-square distribution with non-centrality parameter $2L_0 = 2L(b, a)$ (where b, a are the true values and L is evaluated at the true position p) and $\dim(H_1) - \dim(H_0) = 1$ degree of freedom. Hence,

$$\Pr(L > \Lambda | b, a, p) = F(\Lambda, L_0) \approx \quad (15)$$

$$\approx 2 \exp(-L_0) \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{L_0^j}{j!} \left[Q(\sqrt{2\Lambda}) + (\Lambda/\pi)^{1/2} \exp(-\Lambda/2) \sum_{i=0}^{j-1} \frac{(2\Lambda)^i}{1 \cdot 3 \dots (2i+1)} \right]$$

where $Q(x) = (2\pi)^{-1/2} \int_x^{\infty} \exp(-t^2/2) dt$. The function $F(\Lambda, L_0)$ is shown in Fig. 2.

For $a = 0$, $L_0 = 0$ and we obtain the probability of false detection,

$$P_f = 2Q(\sqrt{2\Lambda}). \quad (16)$$

The average frequency of false detections is obtained by multiplication with the number of 'independent' trial positions per second. It is reasonable to assume that trial positions separated by the FWHM (Full Width at Half Maximum) of the peaks in L_i are fairly independent; thus in a stretch of N samples the number of false detections is estimated as

$$N_f \sim P_f N / (\text{FWHM}), \quad (17)$$

where FWHM is expressed in number of samples. (At 600 Hz sampling rate and 150 arcsec/sec, $\text{FWHM} \approx 3-4$ samples, yielding ~ 1 false detection per second at threshold $\Lambda = 4$.)

The probability of miss, i.e. that a star of given amplitude (a) escapes detection, is

$$P_m = 1 - F[\Lambda, L(b, a)]. \quad (18)$$

From Fig. 2 it is seen that half of the stars at the very threshold of detection ($L_0 = \Lambda$) are missed. The $\pm 1\sigma$ points $P_m = 0.84$ and 0.16 are reached approximately for $L_0 = \Lambda + \frac{1}{2} \pm \sqrt{2\Lambda}$. The sharpness of the detection limit is thus defined by $\pm \sqrt{2\Lambda}$.

2.3. Approximation by means of 'folded filters'

The length of each numerical filter must in reality be $m \gtrsim 100$. Thus, a direct computation of $\hat{a}$ and $\hat{b}$ requires about 200 multiplications and 200 additions. Performing the detection process at two different slit configurations in parallel, at a sampling rate of 600 Hz, would then require more than half a million arithmetic operations per second. A more efficient algorithm is certainly desirable, whether the processing should be performed on board the satellite or on the ground. The Fast Fourier Transform may be a possibility, but the 'folded filter' described below is probably more efficient and much simpler, although it entails a slight loss of estimation accuracy.

The folded filter is applicable when the filter impulse response function can be expressed as the convolution of a simpler (shorter) function with a Dirac comb function. For instance, for $q = 0$, α and β are linear combinations of two filters, one of which is simply the Star Mapper response function f_i . If the grid consists of N parallel identical slits at positions i_s , $s = 1, 2, \dots, N$, we have

$$f_i = \sum_{s=1}^N h(i - i_s) = \sum_j s_j h_{i-j} \quad (19)$$

where $s_j = 1$ if $i_s = j$ for some s , otherwise $s_j = 0$; h_i is the single-slit response function. The output of the filter whose response function is f_i is then

$$\begin{aligned} x_p &= \sum_i f_i n_{i+p} = \sum_i n_{i+p} \sum_j s_j h_{i-j} = \sum_k h_k \sum_j s_j n_{j+k+p} = \\ &= \sum_k h_k y_{k+p}, \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where

$$y_p \equiv \sum_j s_j n_{j+p} = \sum_{s=1}^N n_{p+i_s}. \quad (21)$$

In this example, the output of the 'long' filter f is exactly obtained by computing first the 'folded' sequence y_p (by adding corresponding samples at the different slits) and then running it through the 'short' filter h . The number of multiplications is thereby reduced by a factor N , and almost by another factor of two if h is symmetric (as it will be in practice).

The general filters (6) cannot be exactly represented by folded filters, especially for $q > 0$. Putting

$$\hat{a} = \sum_{k=-K}^K \alpha_k^* y_{k+p}, \quad \hat{b} = \sum_{k=-K}^K \beta_k^* y_{k+p}, \quad (22)$$

where K is a suitable integer, we may however adjust the folded-filter coefficients α_k^* , β_k^* to yield unbiased estimates with minimum variance for any chosen ratio $q = a/b$. The variance of $\hat{a}$ is

$$\sigma_{\hat{a}}^2 = \sum_i (b + af_i) \sum_j \sum_k s_j s_k \alpha_{i-j}^* \alpha_{i-k}^*, \quad (23)$$

and similarly for the variance of $\hat{b}$. Minimizing under the constraints of unbiasedness results in the linear system of equations

$$\begin{array}{|c|} \hline 2K+1 \\ \hline \begin{array}{|c|c|c|} \hline \underline{A} & \underline{d} & \underline{e} \\ \hline \underline{d}' & 0 & 0 \\ \hline \underline{e}' & 0 & 0 \\ \hline \end{array} \\ \hline \end{array} \times \begin{array}{|c|c|} \hline \underline{\alpha}^* & \underline{\beta}^* \\ \hline \cdot & \cdot \\ \hline \cdot & \cdot \\ \hline \end{array} = \begin{array}{|c|c|} \hline \underline{0} & \underline{0} \\ \hline 1 & 0 \\ \hline 0 & 1 \\ \hline \end{array} \quad (24)$$

where the elements of matrix $\underline{A}$ and arrays $\underline{d}$, $\underline{e}$ are

$$A_{kr} = \sum_j s_j s_{j+k-r} (1 + qf_{k+j}), \quad k, r = -K, -K+1, \dots, K; \quad (25)$$

$$d_k = \sum_j s_j f_{j+k}; \quad e_k = N, \quad k = -K, -K+1, \dots, K. \quad (26)$$

2.4. Non-periodic grids

The Star Mapper as described in the Phase A Report (ESA SCI(79)10) consists of two slit systems (grids), one vertical (i.e. perpendicular to the scan) and one inclined at 45° , both grids consisting of eight parallel and equidistant slits. The response function of such a periodic grid is shown (schematically) at the top of Fig. 3. If this is convolved with the amplitude filter (α_i) from eqn (6) one obtains a filter output like the one at the bottom of Fig. 3. (This is essentially an autocorrelation of the response function.) It contains 15 equidistant peaks, with the strongest peak (corresponding to the 'true' location) at the centre, and adjacent peaks not very much weaker. In fact, in the presence of noise it will frequently happen that one of the 'satellite' peaks is stronger, resulting in a positional error of one or two grid periods. This is the so-called slit ambiguity problem characteristic of periodic grids.

Fig. 4 shows the response and filter output when the same number of slits (with the same single-slit response function) is arranged in an irregular fashion, so as to produce satellite peaks which are always much weaker than the central peak. This is achieved by selecting the slit spacings in such a way that the distance between two particular slits does not occur for any other pair of slits, to within a tolerance set by the FWHM of the single-slit response function. For such a non-periodic grid with N slits, the satellite peaks are attenuated by at least a factor $1/N$ compared to the central peak.

At the expense of a longer distance between the extreme slits, it is also possible to devise two mutually exclusive slit configurations for the vertical and inclined grids (Fig. 5). By feeding the same Star Mapper signal through two parallel sets of filters, one set matched to the vertical pattern and one to the inclined, it is possible to detect transits across the two grids with a minimum of interference. Using folded filters, we obtain the algorithmic scheme depicted in Fig. 6.

While the satellite peaks are much weaker for non-periodic configurations, they are also correspondingly more numerous: in principle, $N(N-1)$ satellites is expected in the output of the 'correct' filter (i.e. the one matching the signal), and N^2 satellites in the output of the complementary filter. In reality not all of these satellites are distinct enough to produce separate detections even for the brightest stars (cf. Fig. 5), but a large number of 'ghost detections' are inevitable each time a bright star passes one of the grids.

It should be noted that the optimization of non-periodic configurations e.g. in terms of the shortest arrangement of a given number of slits (with a given FWHM) appears to be a difficult combinatorial problem which I have only attacked by trial and error. The particular configurations shown in Figs. 5-6 and used in the simulations may thus be far from optimum.

3. SIMULATIONS

3.1. Main assumptions and parameters

Several stretches of Star Mapper samples (up to 12 sec duration each) were generated, including a few hundred transits of stars of various magnitudes across both grids (vertical and inclined). The signal was put through two parallel detection/estimation algorithms matched to the non-periodic configurations of Fig. 5. The folded-filter algorithm as outlined in Fig. 6 was used ($N = 8$, $K = 10$).

The Star Mapper response function (f_i) was obtained from (19) with single-slit response function

$$h(x) = r \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \text{sinc}(\pi r u) \text{sinc}(\pi v \Delta t u) \langle \text{OTF}(u\lambda, u\lambda \tan \theta) \rangle \exp(-i2\pi v \Delta t u x) du, \quad (27)$$

where

r = slit width (0.5" for vertical, 0.75" for inclined slits)
(NB: r is measured in the direction of scanning; the width normal to the slit is $r \cos \theta$.)

v = speed of scanning (150"/sec)

Δt = sampling interval (1/600 sec)

θ = inclination of slit (0° for vertical, 45° for inclined)

$\langle \text{OTF} \rangle$ = the two-dimensional optical transfer function of the telescope, averaged with respect to wavelength λ (photoelectron-flux weighted).

The monochromatic optical transfer function $OTF(\eta, \zeta)$ was computed from the theoretical OTF of a rectangular pupil ($0.25 \times 0.10 \text{ m}^2$, linear obstruction ratio = 0.56), on which an arbitrary degradation factor $1 - 0.8(\eta/D)(1 - \eta/D)$ was applied to account for imperfections of the real instrument ($D = 0.25 \text{ m}$ being the length of the entrance pupil in the scanning direction). The effective $\langle OTF \rangle$ was then computed by averaging over the spectral range, using the photon flux distribution of a B-V = 0.75 star, the transmittance profile given by MATRA (Report 60/890, Jan 1980; Fig. 4.7.1, curve 3), and sensitivity type S-20.

The single-slit response functions at $\theta = 0$ and 45° inclination are shown in Figs. 7-8. $h(x)$ as computed from (27) and shown in the figures are normalized in such a way that $h(x) \rightarrow 1$ for $|x| \lesssim r/2$, as $r \rightarrow \infty$. The signal parameter a (amplitude) is defined as the average number of counts per sample that would result from the star if the grid were replaced by a clear plate. $ah(x)$ is then the expected number of counts per sample when the stellar image is at a distance $xv\Delta t$ from the slit (measured in the direction of scanning).

The slit widths used in the simulations, $r = 0.5''$ and $0.75''$ for respectively vertical and inclined slits, were chosen somewhat arbitrarily. The background count rate, $b = 2$ counts per sample (1200 Hz) may be realistic for a 'quiet' photomultiplier and dark sky ($B_{\text{sky}} = 22.5 \text{ mag/arcsec}^2$). A star of magnitude $B = 10$ corresponds roughly to $a = 10$ counts per sample.

3.2. Sample results

Given the signal parameters b , a , and p , photoelectron counts were simulated according to the Poisson distribution with intensity (1). The signal was put through four linear folded filters, producing estimates $\hat{a}$, $\hat{b}$ for both slit configurations. Finally the likelihood ratios L for the vertical and inclined configurations were calculated from eqns (12) and (14). When a local maximum of L was found exceeding the preset level Λ , a position estimate $\hat{p}$ was interpolated and the estimates $\hat{a}$, $\hat{b}$, $\hat{p}$, L_{max} written out.

Fig. 9 shows a transit across the vertical grid of a star of amplitude $a = 4$ ($B \approx 11$). This transit is just detected at a threshold of $\Lambda = 4$. For comparison, Fig. 10 shows the same transit without Poisson randomization of the signal. It is seen that the detection peak is extremely clean; the numerous smaller peaks in Fig. 9 are thus completely spurious, i.e. caused by the photon noise of the background counts.

Figs. 11-12 show transits across both grids of a brighter star ($a = 25$, or $B \approx 9$). The log-likelihood peaks at the correct positions are very strong, but many satellites are also prominent. At threshold $\Lambda = 4$, some 20-30 ghost detection occur for each transit. Fortunately the ghosts are always at fixed (and known) positions with respect to the true detection peak, and can mostly be removed by some simple post-processing of the detection record.

3.3. Comparison with theory

3.3.1. Detection statistics

From a simulated stretch of 7200 samples (12^{s} interval) with no stars brighter than $a = 4$, and with $b = 2$, the number of spurious detections at various threshold levels were counted. The results are given in Table 1 together with expected numbers based on eqns (16) - (17) (FWHM ≈ 2.6 and 6.4 samples for $\theta = 0$ and 45° ; cf. Figs. 7-8).

Table 1. Number of false detections (N_f) for a sequence of $N = 7200$ samples

Threshold Λ	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
N_f (simulations)	283	87	28	9	2	1	0	
N_f (theory)	436	126	40	13	4.4	1.5	0.6	vertical grid
(sim.)/(theory).100%	65	69	70	69	45	67	0	
N_f (simulations)	197	83	37	15	5	1	0	
N_f (theory)	178	52	16	5.3	1.8	0.6	0.2	inclined grid
(sim.)/(theory).100%	111	160	231	283	278	166	0	

If the nominal values of FWHM are adjusted as follows:

$$\text{FWHM} \approx 3.9 (\theta = 0^\circ), \approx 4.8 (\theta = 45^\circ), \quad (28)$$

the predicted number of false detections are in reasonable agreement with the actual numbers obtained in the simulations.

Next 50 transits were simulated of a $B \approx 11$ star ($a = 4$, $b = 2$) crossing the vertical grid. 41 of these were detected at threshold $\Lambda = 4$. Since $L_0 \approx 9.5$ in this case, the theoretical probability of miss, according to (15) and (18), is $P_m = 0.063$. The observed fraction of misses is 0.18.

Of 50 transits of the same star ($a = 4$, $b = 2$) across the inclined grid, 38 were detected. Since $L_0 \approx 6.7$ we have $P_m = 0.20$, compared to the observed fraction 0.24.

If $2L$ is indeed χ^2 distributed we have $E(L) = L_0 + 0.5$ and $\text{Var}(L) = 2L_0 + 0.5$. For the transits detected at $\Lambda = 4$ (which are of course a biased sample), we have the experimental averages and variances as given in Table 2.

Table 2. The average log-likelihood ratio $\langle L \rangle$ and the mean square deviation ($\text{Var}(L)$) from simulations of 100 stellar transits ($a = 4$, $b = 2$), compared with predictions assuming the non-central χ^2 distribution.

	Vertical grid (41 detections)		Inclined grid (38 detections)	
	$\langle L \rangle$	$\text{Var}(L)$	$\langle L \rangle$	$\text{Var}(L)$
observed	10.1	17.2	7.6	10.6
predicted	10.0	19.5	7.2	13.9

In summary it appears that the theoretical distribution of L , and the corresponding number of false detections and misses, are fairly realistic.

3.3.2. Photometric accuracy

By photometric accuracy we mean the relative estimation error of the stellar amplitude parameter (a). This is expressed in magnitudes by the formula

$$\sigma_{ma} = 1.086 (1/a) [\text{Var}(\hat{a})]^{1/2}. \quad (29)$$

(The accuracy of $\hat{b}$, σ_{mb} , is similarly defined.)

For the folded filter used in the simulations (with $q = 0$) we obtain the theoretical expressions from (23) - (26):

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_{ma} &= 1.086 (1/a) [0.120a + 0.320b]^{\frac{1}{2}} && \text{(vertical)} \\ \sigma_{ma} &= 1.086 (1/a) [0.105a + 0.465b]^{\frac{1}{2}} && \text{(inclined)} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (30)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_{mb} &= 1.086 (1/b) [0.0009a + 0.0115b]^{\frac{1}{2}} && \text{(vertical)} \\ \sigma_{mb} &= 1.086 (1/b) [0.0010a + 0.0145b]^{\frac{1}{2}} && \text{(inclined)} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (31)$$

Table 3 gives a comparison with values obtained from the 100 simulated transits.

Table 3. Mean values and dispersions of estimated signal parameters a , b , as obtained in the simulations, and according to theory.

	Vertical grid				Inclined grid			
	$\langle \hat{a} \rangle$	$\langle \hat{b} \rangle$	σ_{ma}	σ_{mb}	$\langle \hat{a} \rangle$	$\langle \hat{b} \rangle$	σ_{ma}	σ_{mb}
observed	4.11	2.15	.24	.09	4.23	2.04	.22	.08
predicted	4	2	.29	.09	4	2	.32	.10

The theoretical formulae (30) - (31) thus give realistic mean errors, possibly even somewhat conservative. That the mean values $\langle \hat{a} \rangle$ are greater than the true value may perhaps be accounted for by the selection effect introduced by the detection threshold (since $L \approx a^2/b$); but then we would also expect $\langle \hat{b} \rangle$ to be less than the true value, which is not the case.

It is interesting to compare the accuracy of the folded filter, (30) - (31), with that of the 'long' filter, (5) - (6). For the latter we have (with $q = 0$)

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_{ma} &= 1.086 (1/a) [0.114a + 0.306b]^{\frac{1}{2}} && \text{(vertical)} \\ \sigma_{ma} &= 1.086 (1/a) [0.101a + 0.450b]^{\frac{1}{2}} && \text{(inclined)} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (32)$$

The difference is only about 2% in the present case ($a = 4$, $b = 2$) - a small price for the computational efficiency of the folded filter algorithm!

3.3.3. Positional accuracy

The lower bound (7) provides a theoretical estimate of the positional accuracy. The sum in brackets depends in a complicated way on the ratio a/b (q in (7)); for the response functions of the simulations we have however to good accuracy

$$\left[\sum_i \frac{[f'(i)]^2}{1 + qf_i} \right]^{-1} \approx \begin{cases} 0.99 + 0.26q & \text{(vertical)} \\ 3.44 + 0.70q & \text{(inclined)} \end{cases} \quad (33)$$

Converting to arcsec (recall that p is in units of $v\Delta t = 0.25$ arcsec) we find

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_{\eta} &\gtrsim (1/a) [0.016a + 0.062b]^{\frac{1}{2}} && [\text{arcsec}] && (\text{vertical}) \\ \sigma_{\eta} &\gtrsim (1/a) [0.044a + 0.22b]^{\frac{1}{2}} && [\text{arcsec}] && (\text{inclined}) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (34)$$

Summary statistics for the positional errors ($\Delta\eta$) obtained in the simulations are given in Table 4. The lower bound (34) is obviously a quite useful estimate.

Table 4. Mean values and rms dispersions of location errors ($\Delta\eta$) of 100 simulated star transits ($a = 4$, $b = 2$).

	Vertical grid (41 detections)		Inclined grid (38 detections)	
	$\langle\Delta\eta\rangle$	disp.	$\langle\Delta\eta\rangle$	disp.
observed	-0".02	0".12	-0".07	0".26
lower bound, (34)	0	0.11	0	0.20

ADDENDUM

After this study was completed Dr A M Cruise (MSSL) drew my attention to the very elegant technique of 'coded apertures' developed for X-ray imaging (Gunson and Polychonopoulos, MNRAS 177, 485, 1976; Fenimore and Cannon, Applied Optics 17, 337, 1978; etc).

The technique makes use of a pseudo-random pattern of slits or holes on a mask, the shadow of which is recorded. The brightness distribution of the luminous source is retrieved by cross-correlating the shadow image with a function matched to the pattern of the mask. By cyclic repetition of the basic pattern, either on the mask or on the decoding function or both, a reconstitution completely free of 'ghosts' (artifacts) is possible, since the convolution of the mask function and the decoding function is strictly zero except for zero lag. The cross-correlation is of course periodic, too, resulting in a certain aliasing of the resulting picture, but this is not a serious problem if the field of view is limited by other means and only a region around its centre is reconstituted.

The absence of ghosts would be an extremely valuable feature if this technique could be applied to the HIPPARCOS Star Mappers. But this is perhaps not possible, due to the infinite length of the photometric sequence, unless the aliasing mentioned above or ghosts at the limits of truncated segments can be accepted.

There is however another kind of finite mask/filter patterns (Fig. 13) for which the cross-correlation is non-positive everywhere except at zero lag. This would be sufficient to suppress the ghosts; the disadvantage is that fainter stars could be hidden in the negative artifacts of a bright star. Unfortunately I have not been able to construct such patterns for more than three slits (top and middle of Fig. 13). Below in Fig. 13 is a mask/filter pair with four slits for which the positive sidelobes are only 1/20 of the central peak; not perfect, but close enough.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of detection/estimation algorithm. The signal amplitude (a) and background level (b) are continuously estimated by means of linear filters. Detection occurs when a local maximum of the test statistic $L(\hat{a}, \hat{b})$ exceeds a preselected threshold Λ .

Fig. 2. Probability that a log-likelihood-ratio peak (L) exceeds a threshold value Λ . $L_0 = L(b, a)$ is the expected log-likelihood-ratio, given the true parameters $p, a,$ and b .

Fig. 3. Top: Star Mapper response function (model signal) obtained with a grid consisting of 8 equidistant slits (periodic grid). Bottom: output of the α -filter estimating the amplitude of the model signal shown at top of figure. The central peak gives the true amplitude (apart from a scaling factor); the other peaks are 'satellites'. The filter output is essentially the autocorrelation function of the model signal.

Fig. 4. With a non-periodic arrangement of the same 8 slits as in Fig. 3 the satellite peaks of the filter output are strongly suppressed.

Fig. 5. Top: Star Mapper response functions (model signals) for two slit configurations with minimum cross-correlation. Below: filter outputs when the model signals above are put through the two α -filters matched to the different configurations. Superscript (1) and (2) refer to respectively the vertical and inclined slits. $\circledast$ denotes convolution.

Fig. 6. Folded-filter algorithm for estimation of signal parameters, for the response functions of Fig. 5.

Fig. 7. Single-slit response function for vertical slits ($\theta = 0^\circ$) of various widths: $r = 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 1.0$ arcsec. Slit width $r = 0.5$ arcsec was used for Fig. 5 and all simulations. The distance scale on the abscissa is in units of $v\Delta t = 0.25$ arcsec.

Fig. 8. Single-slit response function for inclined slits ($\theta = 45^\circ$) of widths $r = 0.75, 1.00, 1.25, 1.50, 1.75, 2.00, 2.25, 2.50, 2.75, 3.00$ arcsec. The width $r = 0.75$ arcsec was used in the simulations. Scales as in Fig. 7.

Fig. 9. Simulation of a star crossing the vertical slit system (stellar amplitude $a = 4$, corresponding to 11th magnitude; background level $b = 2$ counts/sample). First graph (top): individual photon counts (n_i). Transits at individual slits are indicated by arrows. Second to fourth graph: output of linear α - and β -filters, estimating $\hat{a}$ and $\hat{b}$, and the log-likelihood ratio L . With detection threshold $\Lambda = 4$ (dashed line) the star is detected at the correct instant. The bottom three graphs show the filter outputs and log-likelihood ratio for the filters matched to the inclined slit system. One spurious detection occurs at $\Lambda = 4$.

Fig. 10. Same experiment as in Fig. 9, but without Poisson noise on the photometric samples (n_i).

Fig. 11. Simulation of a brighter star ($a = 25$, or $B \approx 9$) crossing the vertical slit system. Note the large number of 'ghost' detections (at threshold $\Lambda = 4$) for both filter systems.

Fig. 12. Simulation of a star ($a = 25$) crossing the inclined slit system.

Fig. 13. Examples of mask/filter combinations with complete or almost complete suppression of ghosts (see Addendum).